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Cost-effective mass cultivation of *Arthrospira platensis* using NPK fertilizer-based media in outdoor raceway ponds

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Commercial production of *Spirulina* (*Arthrospira platensis*) is expanding rapidly worldwide due to its superior nutritional profile, high protein content, and diverse industrial applications. However, large-scale cultivation is often limited by the high cost of conventional nutrient media, particularly Zarrouk's formulation. This study evaluates the growth performance, biomass productivity, and economic feasibility of NPK fertilizer-based media as a low-cost alternative for mass *Spirulina* cultivation under tropical post-monsoon conditions. Comparative experiments were conducted in semi-outdoor tanks (80 L) and subsequently scaled up to a 20,000 L outdoor raceway pond. In the 80 L systems, NPK medium significantly enhanced growth, achieving a higher specific growth rate (0.223 day^{-1}), shorter doubling time (3.11 days), and increased biomass concentration ($309 \times 10^3 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$) compared to standard and modified Zarrouk's media ($p < 0.05$). The large-scale raceway pond trial further validated the efficiency of the NPK medium, yielding 1.4 g L^{-1} (dry weight) within a 15-day production cycle under optimal environmental conditions ($22\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$; pH 8.5–10; salinity 4–5‰; DO 5–7 mg L^{-1}). Proximate composition analysis confirmed high nutritional quality of the harvested biomass, containing 56.2% protein, 4.8% lipid, 2.4% fiber, 6% moisture, and 8.7% ash. Economic assessment revealed a production cost of 1,040 BDT/kg ($\approx 8.5 \text{ USD/kg}$) and a market return of 1,352 BDT/kg ($\approx 11 \text{ USD/kg}$), resulting in a 30% profit margin. Overall, NPK-based media provides a sustainable, scalable, and cost-effective solution for mass production of high-quality *Spirulina* in tropical outdoor aquaculture systems.

Keywords: *Spirulina*, NPK, Raceway, Biomass, Productivity

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